

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Drug Repurposing: Uncovering New Uses for Existing Medications

S. Showbharnikhaa¹, M.K. Vijayalakshmi²

¹Final Year B. Pharmacy Student, Faculty of Pharmacy, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Selaiyur, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

²Associate Professor, Faculty of Pharmacy, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Selaiyur, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

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Abstract: Drug repurposing, also known as drug repositioning or reprofiling, refers to the process of identifying new therapeutic applications for existing drugs that were originally intended for different medical indications. This approach has gained prominence as an attractive alternative to traditional new drug development due its significant advantages of lower costs, reduced risks, and quicker delivery of treatment options to patients. By leveraging extensive safety and pharmacokinetic data already established for approved or investigational drugs, drug repurposing can expedite various stages of the drug development pipeline. Notable strategies employed in repurposing existing drugs include serendipitous discoveries, data mining large datasets to reveal potential drug-disease connections, high-throughput screening of compound libraries, and observations from clinical practice. Some successful examples that demonstrate the promise of this approach are aspirin now being used to prevent cardiovascular diseases, thalidomide addressing multiple myeloma and leprosy, and metformin investigated for cancer treatment beyond managing diabetes. While intellectual property protection, clinical trials, and funding pose challenges, ongoing advances in technology and disease insights are likely to further the prospects of drug repurposing improving healthcare worldwide.

Keywords: Drug repurposing, Drug repositioning, Drug development, Existing drugs, New therapeutic applications.

1. Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of medical research and drug development, the concept of drug repurposing has emerged as a promising and innovative approach. Also known as drug repositioning or reprofiling, it involves the exploration of new therapeutic applications for existing medications originally intended for different medical indications. Drug development is a time-consuming and costly process, often taking over a decade and costing billions of dollars to bring a new drug from the research stage to market approval. Moreover, the high failure rate of new drug candidates poses a substantial challenge to the pharmaceutical industry. In light of these obstacles, drug repurposing, also known as drug repositioning or reprofiling, has emerged as a promising strategy to identify new therapeutic applications for existing drugs. This approach leverages the safety and pharmacokinetic profiles of approved or investigational drugs to expedite the development of treatments for a wide range of diseases and conditions. This method has gained considerable attention for its substantial advantages, including cost-effectiveness, reduced risks, and accelerated delivery of treatment options to patients. By capitalizing on the wealth of safety and pharmacokinetic data already associated with approved or investigational drugs, drug repurposing has the potential to streamline various phases of the drug development process. This article delves into the world of drug repurposing, exploring the strategies employed, showcasing successful case studies, and addressing the challenges and future prospects of this innovative approach. In doing so, it highlights the transformative potential of repurposing existing drugs to advance global healthcare.

2. The Essence of Drug Repurposing:

Drug repurposing is the process of identifying and validating new uses for drugs that were originally developed for different indications. This approach has garnered attention for several compelling reasons:

Cost-Efficiency: Repurposing existing drugs can significantly reduce the cost and time required for drug development. The early stages of preclinical and clinical testing are often expedited since extensive safety and pharmacokinetic data already exist for these compounds.

* Corresponding author: S. Showbharnikhaa

Reduced Risk: Drugs that have been approved for human use have undergone rigorous safety and efficacy assessments. This reduces the risks associated with developing new chemical entities, which might not demonstrate safety or efficacy during later stages of development.

Expanded Patient Access: Repurposed drugs can rapidly provide new treatment options for patients with unmet medical needs. This is especially critical for rare diseases or conditions with limited therapeutic options.

Sustainability: Drug repurposing aligns with sustainable healthcare practices by reducing the demand for new drug development, which often involves resource-intensive processes.

3. Approaches to drug repurposing:

The following strategies are employed in the process of drug repurposing:

Serendipity: Historically, many drug discoveries were made serendipitously. For example, Viagra, originally developed as a treatment for angina, was found to have an unexpected side effect that led to its use in erectile dysfunction.

Data Mining: Advances in bioinformatics allow researchers to analyze large datasets of biological and clinical information to identify potential drug-disease connections. This approach relies on understanding the molecular mechanisms of diseases and matching them with drugs that can target those mechanisms.

High-Throughput Screening: *In vitro* and *in vivo* screening of compound libraries can reveal existing drugs with activity against new disease targets. This method often includes assessing thousands of compounds for potential repurposing.

Pharmacology: This approach explores the intricate network of molecular interactions within a cell to identify potential drug-disease connections. Drugs are evaluated not just for their primary target but for their effects on the entire network.

Observations and Trials: Sometimes, the most compelling evidence for drug repurposing comes from observations in clinical practice. In these cases, healthcare professionals notice that a drug used for one condition also provides benefits for another condition, leading to formal clinical trials to confirm its efficacy.

4. Successful examples of drug repurposing

Following notable examples highlight the success of drug repurposing:

Aspirin: Originally developed as a pain reliever and anti-inflammatory medication, aspirin is now widely used to prevent heart attacks and strokes.

Thalidomide: Although notorious for its teratogenic effects in the 1950s, thalidomide has found new life as a treatment for multiple myeloma and leprosy.

Metformin: Initially prescribed to manage type 2 diabetes, metformin is being investigated for its potential in cancer treatment and prevention.

Antivirals: Existing antiviral medications, like remdesivir and ivermectin, have been examined for their effectiveness against various viral infections, including COVID-19.

5. Challenges and future prospects

While drug repurposing offers significant advantages, it is not without challenges. Key hurdles include the need for intellectual property protection for the repurposed use, conducting clinical trials to confirm safety and efficacy, and securing financial support for the necessary research. Looking ahead, advancements in artificial intelligence, high-throughput screening, and our understanding of disease mechanisms will continue to drive drug repurposing efforts. This approach holds immense potential in finding new treatments for a wide range of diseases, ultimately benefiting patients, reducing healthcare costs, and promoting sustainability in drug development.

Conclusion

Drug repurposing, a process that uncovers new therapeutic applications for existing medications, offers numerous advantages, including lower costs, reduced risks, and quicker delivery of treatment options. Various strategies, such as serendipitous discoveries and data mining, are employed to identify new uses for existing drugs. Successful examples like aspirin, thalidomide, and metformin demonstrate the potential of this approach. Despite challenges related to intellectual property protection, clinical trials, and funding, ongoing technological advances and increased disease insights are expected to further enhance the potential of drug repurposing in improving healthcare worldwide.

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Author's short biography

S.Showbharnikhaa:

S.Showbharnikhaa , B.Pharm Final year student at Faculty of Pharmacy, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research.

M.K. Vijayalakshmi:

M.K. Vijayalakshmi is working as an Associate Professor in department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry /Analysis at Faculty of Pharmacy, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research. She has completed her post-graduation in Pharmaceutical Chemistry in Madaras Medical College, Chennai. She has vast experience in Research and Development in various industries and Organisation. Her present interest on research in Computer Aided Drug Design with strong background in various pharmaceutical field as Quality Control Chemist, Senior Research Scientist and Academic Field. She has published many number of research article in peer reviewed national and international journals and many number of book chapters and also she edited many books.